

PROCEDURES FOR PROVIDING OPERATIONAL ASSISTANCE FOR FAMILY PLANNING AT THE POPULATION CONTROL AND FAMILY PLANNING SERVICE OF EAST BOLAANG MONGONDOW REGENCY

Vaykel Marshal Mokobimbing^{a, 1*}, Ferdinand Kerebungu^{b, 2}, Recky H. E. Sendouw^{c, 3}

^{ab}Universitas Negeri Manado, Tondano, Indonesia

¹ vaykelmarshal@gmail.com *; ² ferdinandkerebungu@unima.ac.id, ³ reckysendouw@unima.ac.id

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Abstract

This study aims to determine, describe, analyze and interpret the procedure for providing Family Planning Operational Assistance (BOKB) at the Population and Family Planning Control Office of East Bolaang Mongondow Regency and identify the determinant factors that influence the procedure for providing BOKB. This study uses a qualitative approach. Data collection was carried out by means of interviews, observation and documentation. The results of the study indicate that the procedure for providing family planning operational assistance (BOKB) at the Population and Family Planning Control Office of East Bolaang Mongondow Regency has not been fully implemented optimally because there are still procedures that are not as in the SOP, namely delays in disbursement of funds, the ability of implementers in compiling documents, verification of recipient lists experiencing time and human resource limitations as well as geographical conditions in remote areas, the determination of recipient lists is not optimal in terms of transparency and information delivery to the community, the processing of BOKB funds is limited in administrative capabilities and human resources as well as error network access and determinant factors that influence such as the coverage of active KB participants and the number of PUS, the performance of field officers/PLKB, geographical location, implementation performance and budget realization.

Keyword: Procedures for Providing Family Planning Operational Assistance, PPKB Service.

INTRODUCTION

Population growth directly impacts efforts to improve the quality of human resource utilization. Population growth is a primary source of human resource development, which requires guidance, development, and utilization. Population control is essential to ensure that prosperity is enjoyed by all, to reduce poverty, and to provide access to basic services for all levels of society [1]. The government's goal is to achieve balanced population growth and quality families. The government has established a family planning policy through the implementation of a family planning program in accordance with Law Number 52 of 2009 concerning Population Development and Family Development. The family planning policy aims to regulate unwanted pregnancies, including maintaining health and reducing maternal, infant, and child mortality rates, improving access to and quality of information, education, counseling, and family planning services, increasing male participation and involvement in family planning practices, and promoting breastfeeding as an effort to space pregnancies (BKKBN, 2022).

Law Number 23 of 2014 concerning Regional Government explains that population control and family planning (KB) are mandatory government affairs that are not related to basic services and their authority is concurrently the authority of the central government, provinces, districts and cities. To support national priority programs in population control and family planning that are the responsibility of regional governments, it is necessary to provide special non-physical allocation funds in the form of operational assistance for family planning (BOKB).[2] BOKB is a fund allocated to regions to finance the operational activities of national priority programs in the implementation of population control and family planning affairs that are regional affairs in order to improve the achievement of the implementation of family development, population, and family planning programs. BOKB funds allocated to certain regions aim to implement activities adjusted to regional authority in supporting efforts to achieve priority targets for family development, population, and family planning and stunting reduction (BKKBN

Regulation No. 4 of 2024). The management of the Family Planning Fund (BOKB), in the context of regional autonomy, is part of regional financial management, encompassing planning, budgeting, implementation, administration, reporting, and financial accountability. The BOKB is distributed to regions and managed directly by the regional family planning organization (OPD-KB). Financial management in public organizations, including the OPD-KB, is crucial because the public sector, unlike the private sector, has a moral obligation and responsibility to provide for various economic segments, including assistance for the underprivileged, such as the Family Hope Program, non-cash food assistance (BPNT), direct cash assistance, and other types of assistance directly targeted at the community (Bastian, 2020). Suboptimal management can impact the low effectiveness of a program, [3]including the family planning program funded by the BOKB, which can affect the achievement of population development indicators.

In East Bolaang Mongondow Regency, Family Planning Operational Assistance (BOKB) is a crucial funding source for supporting and strengthening the implementation of the Population, Family Planning, and Family Development (Bangga Kencana) program. The BOKB is allocated to finance the management and implementation of Family Planning Extension Center activities, in accordance with the allocated budget. This primarily addresses the aspects of outreach, cadre mobilization, family planning services, data quality improvement, cross-sectoral networking, and stunting prevention. The success of family development and population control programs at the regional level depends heavily on the smooth operation of field implementers. The use of BOKB funds for the distribution of contraceptive devices and drugs is based on health facilities registered with the National Population and Family Planning Agency (BKKBN). The Regional Apparatus Organization (OPD-KB) develops implementation guidelines (juklak) for BOKB implementation, referring to the BOKB technical manual.

However, an interesting phenomenon emerged when the disbursement procedures, which involved strict administrative reporting of BOKB funds, were perceived as an additional burden for field extension workers. Extension workers often found themselves caught up in the complex administrative demands of "Accountability Letters" (SPJ), resulting in time that should have been allocated for community education being consumed by clerical matters. Furthermore, in planning, there is a discrepancy between the transportation cost standards set out in the technical guidelines and the actual transportation costs in the difficult terrain of East Bolaang Mongondow, creating gaps in the policy's implementation. Available operational funding for services comes only from the BOKB Fund, while regional budget (APBD) funding is not yet available. Furthermore, the provision of central government funding has not been sufficient or adequate to meet the actual needs and conditions in recipient areas. Furthermore, recipient areas sometimes experience delays in disbursement of BOKB funds.

Stunting management funded by the BOKB consists of sensitive interventions that indirectly address the causes of stunting, such as outreach and education related to behavioral change. The quality of TPK cadres remains poor due to a lack of training, and the program is not structured to suit regional conditions. The availability of contraceptive devices and drugs funded by the BOKB is insufficient to meet the needs of active family planning participants. For example, active family planning participants must take pills every month, but the availability of pills funded by the BOKB funds runs out at health facilities, resulting in participants purchasing them themselves at pharmacies. SOPs for contraceptive distribution are not yet available. A Regent's Regulation governing the guaranteed availability of contraceptives is not yet available. Other non-technical obstacles, such as the turnover of cadres from each village, ultimately hamper the payment/distribution of operational support funded by the BOKB. The number of claims for installation and removal of implants and IUDs funded by the BOKB is not appropriate, resulting in some not being paid. BOKB funding support to work with unmet need fertile age couples (couples who do not want any more children but do not want to use family planning) in the form of IEC and mentoring is inadequate.

Another issue is that Family Planning Extension Workers (PKB) and Family Assistance Team (TPK) cadres face challenging geographic realities, from mountainous areas to hard-to-reach coastal areas. Initial observations indicate that these mobilization activities are often hampered by budget support mechanisms deemed inadequate to address the real needs of remote villages. In several allocations of funds for basic service needs such as BOK at the Community Health Center managed by the District Health Office and BOKB KB Counseling Center in the Sub-district managed by the Population and Family Planning Control Office, it seems necessary to review the relevance of the authority of each institution as a health service unit and a family planning service unit. The provision of services carried out by both institutions—in accordance with the Tupoksi—must have clear targets and the number of service recipients (beneficiaries). It becomes difficult and has the potential for bias in determining the amount of fund allocation if the target beneficiaries who must be served by the institution are unclear who they will be using the service unit (Dewi, 2023).

The BOKB Fund, a special non-physical allocation fund from the central government, should be a solution to these operational obstacles. This policy is designed to ensure that all counseling activities, contraceptive services, and support for families at risk of stunting have a definite financial backing. Administratively, the BOKB budget absorption at the Population Control and Family Planning Office of East Bolaang Mongondow Regency is quite significant, but at the grassroots level, complaints persist regarding complicated claim procedures and delays in incentives for cadres. Although the BOKB budget in East Bolaang Mongondow Regency has increased year after year, implementation of this policy continues to face challenges. The following table shows the BOKB budget realization in East Bolaang Mongondow Regency.

Table 1. Realization of the BOKB Budget for East Bolaang Mongondow Regency for 2021-2024

Year	Budget	Realization
2021	Rp. 1,720,567,219,-	Rp. 1,670,137,912,-
2022	Rp. 1,785,447,982,-	Rp. 1,785,447,982,-
2023	Rp. 2,527,991,046,-	Rp. 2,495,667,185,-
2024	Rp. 2,674,315,897,-	Rp. 2,635,991,672,-

The table above shows that BOKB budget realization has increased annually, but this is not enough to influence the success of the Bangsa Kencana program. The program's success depends not only on budget size but also on overall policy implementation. Theoretically, the success of a policy is determined not only by the availability of funds (Resources), but also by how the policy message is communicated (Communication), the behavioral tendencies of implementers (Disposition), and the bureaucratic flow that supports it [4]. The mismatch between centralized technical instructions and diverse local conditions in East Bolaang Mongondow indicates obstacles in the process of policy transmission from the central to the regional levels.

According to Nugroho, policy implementation is essentially a way for a policy to achieve its objectives, which is further explained as neither more nor less [5]. Implementation concerns the extent to which the programmed direction is truly satisfactory. Meter and Horn in Subarsono attempt to adopt a policy system model that essentially involves several components that must always be present so that policy demands can be realized into policy outcomes [6]. There are 5 indicators to measure the success of policy implementation, including policy standards and objectives, implementing organization resources, communication between organizations and implementing activities, disposition/attitude of implementers, social, economic, and political conditions. This study aims to determine the procedures for providing operational assistance for family planning (BOKB) at the Population Control and Family Planning Service of East Bolaang Mongondow Regency and the determinant factors that influence it.

METHOD

This research uses a qualitative approach. [7] This approach was chosen because it is able to explore the hidden meaning behind the phenomenon of operational assistance procedures for family planning (BOKB) so that the problems studied can be understood more comprehensively, deeply, naturally, and as they are without excessive intervention from the researcher on the facts in the field. The focus of this research is the stages of providing operational family planning assistance at the Population Control and Family Planning Office of East Bolaang Mongondow Regency. To analyze the stages of providing operational family planning assistance, the following parameters/sub-focuses were used:

1. Recipient List
2. Distribution SOP
3. Verify Recipient List
4. Determination of Recipient
5. Fund Processing

The primary instrument in this study was the researcher herself (human instrument), who served as planner, data collector, analyst, interpreter, and reporter of research results, as is customary in qualitative research. Supporting instruments used included a semi-structured interview guide based on the four research focuses, an observation sheet

to record the physical condition of infrastructure and the availability of information media, and a voice recorder for interview documentation. The interview guide was flexible, allowing the researcher to develop further questions (probing) according to the dynamics of responses and situations that arose in the field. The types of data collected consist of primary data and secondary data, where primary data is obtained directly from in-depth interviews with five key informants and field observations, while secondary data is sourced from official village documents, laws and regulations, and relevant scientific literature.[8]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Recipient List

The mechanism for determining the list of recipients of operational assistance for family planning (BOKB) by the Population and Family Planning Control Office of East Bolaang Mongondow Regency certainly goes through a number of series of processes. This process involves various parties both at the district level in this case the PPKB Office and involvement at the Village level. In accordance with BKKBN Regulation No. 14 of 2023, BOKB recipients include a list of acceptors for family planning service recipients, field line operations including PUS, Prospective Women, Pregnant Women, Postpartum Women, the elderly and families who are members of groups including UPPKA, field extension operations (PLKB both recording reporting and KB Villages which also include target groups including PUS, Prospective Women, Adolescents, Pregnant Women, Postpartum Women and Toddlers as well as families at risk of stunting.

Interviews with several informants revealed that the process of compiling the list of BOKB aid recipients begins with data collection by field officers in their respective work areas. These officers, in this case the PLKB, are well-versed in the conditions on the ground. Actively targeted families, in addition to field data, are also matched with SIGA data to ensure accuracy. In addition, from the results of the interviews that have been conducted, it is known that in terms of determining the list of recipients, it refers to the existing regulations through technical guidelines issued by the Ministry of Education and Culture/BKKBN which emphasizes that BOKB recipients include active KB activity targets and priority target groups in KB villages such as families at risk of stunting, pregnant women, prospective brides and grooms, PUS and other operational matters.

However, public complaints were also found regarding the suboptimal recipient list, due to some people's lack of awareness of the Family Planning Operational Assistance (BOKB). Interviews revealed that these complaints stem from people not yet on the recipient list and feeling eligible, even though the recipient list was determined based on the criteria outlined in the technical guidelines. According to George Charles Edward III [9], one of the weaknesses in the public policy process, particularly in Indonesia, is poor communication during implementation. Regarding the determination of the recipient list, some members of the public were unaware of the BOKB funds, demonstrating that communication can influence whether or not information is fully conveyed to the public. Communication should be established so that the material that will form the basis of a policy can be understood and adapted to evolving needs.

Distribution SOP

Family planning operational assistance (BOKB) is a Non-Physical DAK for the Family Planning Sub-sector allocated to certain regions to carry out activities tailored to regional authority in supporting efforts to achieve priority targets for family development, population and family planning, and stunting reduction (BKKBN Regulation No. 4 of 2024). The process of distributing family planning operational assistance (BOKB) funds is based on technical instructions issued by the Ministry of Education and Culture/BKKBN. [10] In general, the distribution of operational assistance for family planning begins with the central government through the Non-Physical Special Allocation Fund (DAK) mechanism, which is then channeled to the regional treasury in each district/city on a quarterly basis. Once the BOKB is received by the regional treasury, the funds can be managed by the district/city government through the Population Control and Family Planning Office, and then used for field activities according to the designated allocation and programs.

Based on interviews with several informants, it was stated that there are SOPs in the form of technical guidelines from the ministry, specifically the Ministry of Education and Culture/BKKBN. These guidelines regulate everything from planning and implementation to reporting. However, it's important to note that in its implementation, some PLKBs and cadres still don't fully understand the detailed distribution procedures. Overall, the distribution SOP has been running well and in accordance with the provisions, although it is recognized that sometimes there are still obstacles in the preparation of documents by the implementers which result in delays in the disbursement of BOKB funds. According to George Charles Edward III [9], if human resources in terms of quantity and quality that meet policy requirements are not optimally met, it will affect the implementation of the policy. Regarding the distribution SOP, in preparing documents for the disbursement of BOKB funds, there are still obstacles in the preparation of

documents by implementers due to the limited number of implementers and the uneven understanding of implementers. Furthermore, the existence of lengthy SOP procedures/mechanisms is certainly related to the bureaucratic structure that regulates the work of implementers.

Verify Recipient List

Verifying the list of recipients of operational family planning assistance (BOKB) is a crucial step in ensuring that the proposed data meets the existing requirements and criteria for potential BOKB recipients. The primary objective of this verification process is to ensure that the prospective recipients proposed by field officers correctly and convincingly meet all the criteria outlined in the technical guidelines for implementing BOKB-funded programs. According to the technical instructions stipulated in BKKBN Regulation No. 4 of 2024, the administrative completeness of beneficiaries (e.g. service acceptors) that must be verified includes: List of acceptor names (by name by address), photocopy of KTP/Domicile Certificate, photocopy of K/IV/KB card and recapitulation of the list of recipient acceptors.

Based on interviews with several informants, the verification process involves direct visits and checking with targeted families. This verification process also involves PPKBD cadres and village government officials to ensure smooth operation. In addition to field verification, SIGA data (administrative data) is also reviewed. This is crucial for improving data accuracy and accountability. Overall, the verification process for prospective BOKB fund recipients in East Bolaang Mongondow Regency has gone well. However, it's important to recognize that not all data can be verified optimally in the field due to time and resource constraints. This is also influenced by geographic conditions, particularly in mountainous and coastal areas. Furthermore, the verification process is sometimes hampered by the absence of targeted families or even their relocation, which can hinder the process.

Edward III stated that several indicators influence public policy implementation, particularly in terms of communication, one of which is clarity [9]. Clarity is an absolute must in policy implementation. Regarding disbursement procedures, particularly in verifying recipient lists, clear communication and appropriate methods are essential. This clear communication can minimize erroneous or suboptimal field coordination. Furthermore, human resource factors can influence this verification stage.

Determination of Recipient

Determining recipients of the Family Planning Operational Assistance (BOKB) Fund is a crucial process to ensure that the budget for family planning and stunting reduction is properly targeted. Targets and recipients must align with field control register data and the Bangga Kencana Program baseline data, as well as the Family Data Collection (BKKBN Regulation No. 4 of 2024). Determining recipients of operational family planning assistance (BOKB) funds is a follow-up process after the verification of the prospective recipient list has been completed. This determination of recipients is carried out through administrative stages through the issuance of a Decree (SK) by the Regent. The decree lists the names of recipients or target groups who have gone through all existing verification processes, both administratively and in the field, and are therefore deemed to meet the criteria.

Based on the results of interviews with several informants, the final authority in determining the list of recipients lies with the Head of the Service as the person responsible for the program and the authorized budget user (KPA) to then be proposed to the Regent to issue a Decree signed by the Regent. However, the decision must still be based on the results of verification that has been carried out jointly by both the service through administrative verification and verification in the field through field officers and on technical recommendations from related fields so that it is not done unilaterally and of course on target and based on formal procedures and a clear legal basis. The determination of recipients sometimes encounters obstacles or changes, even after the decree has been issued, due to targeted families changing domiciles and a perceived lack of transparency from the community. Decrees can also be amended at any time if it is discovered that a family or community member within the targeted group has moved. Therefore, the decree needs to be adjusted, and the data in SIGA as recipients does not match the actual data on the ground. We will immediately report this to the Agency for adjustments to the recipient decree.

The recipient determination process has generally proceeded well and in accordance with formal procedures, which have a clear legal basis for issuing decrees. Although challenges with transparency and the dissemination of information to the public are sometimes encountered, increased outreach is needed to avoid suspicions that could lead to polemics or problems in the village. According to Edward III's approach, disposition is the implementer's attitude and commitment regarding policy implementation [9]. Regarding the BOKB granting procedure, in the context of determining recipients, disposition will not be effective if the implementer is unable to respond to the needs and expectations of the community. However, it is important to recognize that the implementer is still focused solely on procedures, not on public needs. Furthermore, regarding communication, implementers must establish good

communication to create transparency of information for the public, especially regarding the determination of the recipient list.

Fund Processing

Management must comply with the BKKBN Technical Instructions (Juknis), which involve planning, use of the Krisna/Morena application, recording, and tiered reporting. Financial management of the BOKB within the APBD is carried out in accordance with statutory provisions (BKKBN Regulation No. 4 of 2024). Management of Family Planning Operational Assistance includes the preparation of fund utilization plans, budgeting, activity implementation, reporting, and accountability. The planning stages for the use of the BOKB budget will be developed according to the needs for field activities proposed by field officers/PLKB. These proposals will then be outlined in a work budget plan (RKA), which will refer to technical guidelines issued by the Ministry of Education and Culture/BKKBN. This plan will cover all activities related to the KB Village program, family planning services, outreach, IEC, and the operational activities of extension workers and cadres.

Based on interviews with several informants, the planning process for the budget work plan (RKA) inevitably involves implementing activities, including field officers, while still coordinating with the agency. This process is carried out by adjusting actual needs in the field to the available budget allocation. It is important to realize that not all proposals can be fully accommodated, as we must, once again, adjust to actual needs in the field and the available budget. In this planning, SIGA data is the primary data, adjusted to actual field data. Based on this data, we can develop programs together with the agency to align with the budget allocations from the center, including family planning services, extension worker and cadre operations, extension services, and others.

Furthermore, for the implementation stage, the Family Planning Operational Assistance (BOKB) will be used to support various activities and operations of the Family Planning program. The implementation of these activities will involve every field officer, especially in their respective work areas. Then the role of all cadres, both PPKBD and Sub PPKBD, as well as families and communities who are the targets and targets of the program. This Family Planning Operational Assistance will be used to finance operations such as family planning services, meetings with target groups including the Elderly Family Development (BKL), Toddler Family Development (BKB), and Youth Family Development (BKR), counseling and IEC, and other activities.

Reporting is also a mandatory step in administrative compliance, particularly regarding fund management. Implemented activities must be reported and accompanied by an accountability document or accountability letter (SPJ). This report is prepared by the activity implementer and then forwarded to the treasurer for further review. For the accountability stage, the report that has been made will later be checked and examined by the service to see whether it is in accordance with the provisions regarding the use of funds, and will then become an official report which can then be examined as part of supervision by the Inspectorate or the BPK. Based on the results of interviews with several informants, the reporting and accountability system is implemented through the process of preparing an Accountability Letter (SPJ) for each activity that has been carried out. The Accountability Letter (SPJ) must be complete and accompanied by physical evidence in the form of an attendance list of activity participants, receipts, activity documentation, activity materials and an overall activity report.

On the other hand, reporting of BOKB funds is also carried out through government financial reporting applications such as Morena, Krisna, and EPRA in accordance with applicable regulations. Supervision of BOKB funds by the Ministry of Education and Culture/BKKBN and the Inspectorate is routine every year and also in conjunction with the BPK, where to ensure that the use of funds is in accordance with applicable rules and technical instructions. From the explanation above, overall, the processing of BOKB funds has been carried out well. However, there are also undeniable issues that sometimes arise in reporting and accountability, namely technical obstacles such as human error, or natural human error or limited administrative capabilities, which often lead to delays. Henri Fayol (1979) stated that administrative principles such as planning, organizing, controlling and evaluating must be applied in financial management including the processing of operational assistance for family planning (BOKB).

According to Edward III, [9]resources, especially human resources as implementers, must be able to implement public policies, including procedures and management of BOKB to meet the needs of the community. Research conducted by Kerebunu and Fathimah confirms that the process of implementing community empowerment policies must be carried out in stages and on target to be successful. The results of the study indicate that the success of a public intervention program does not only depend on budget availability, but is also determined by three crucial stages in the empowerment process: awareness, capacity building, and empowerment. Furthermore, this study identified that program failure is often caused by inaccurate targeting (right on target), as well as a lack of attention to the local context or situation and the timing factor in implementation. This finding is in line with the focus of research on the procedures for providing Family Planning Operational Assistance (BOKB), where clear

communication, adequate resources, and an understanding of the geographic and social conditions of the community are determining factors for the success of policy implementation.[11] Similarly, research conducted by Poluakan, Kantohe, and Lontoh (2024) demonstrated that financial accountability and transparency simultaneously have a significant impact on financial management in local governments. The analysis showed that partially, financial accountability has a positive impact on financial management, indicating that good accountability in the management of official finances can provide positive contributions and benefits for local government financial management. Furthermore, transparency has also been shown to have a positive impact, indicating that the higher the level of openness within the government, the better the quality of financial management. This finding is highly relevant to research on the procedures for providing Family Planning Operational Assistance (BOKB), where accountability in fund management and transparency in determining the recipient list are determining factors influencing the success of policy implementation.[12]

CONCLUSION

Based on the discussion of the research results that have been conducted, it can be concluded that the procedure for providing operational assistance for family planning (BOKB) in East Bolaang Mongondow Regency, in compiling the list of recipients, SOP for distribution, verification of the list of recipients, determination of recipients and processing of funds has been carried out in accordance with the distribution procedure but has not yet been fully implemented optimally to achieve the objectives of the program. This still involves suboptimal procedures, such as delays in fund disbursement procedures and delays in document preparation. Furthermore, time and human resource constraints are still present in the verification of recipient lists. This is also influenced by geographic conditions, particularly in mountainous and coastal areas, as well as remote areas. Furthermore, transparency and dissemination of information to the public are not optimal in determining the recipient list, requiring improved communication and outreach. In the processing of Family Planning Operational Assistance (BOKB) funds, technical constraints are encountered, such as human error, or limited administrative capabilities/resources, and network access errors, resulting in frequent delays in planning and reporting. The determinant factors that influence this are: the coverage of active KB participants and the number of fertile age couples (PUS), the performance of PLKB and their number, geographical location and conditions, the number of KB Villages, the performance of budget implementation and realization as well as national priority policies and programs.

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